

Electrochemical Behaviour of Symmetrically Disubstituted Azobenzene in Buffered Media

P. N. GUPTA* and ANJU RAINA

Department of Chemistry, University of Kashmir, Srinagar-190 006

Manuscript received 5 January 1989, accepted 22 July 1989

Reduction behaviour of 2,2'-dichloroazobenzene and 2,2'-dimethylazobenzene in well buffered media over a broad pH range has been investigated employing various electrochemical techniques. Depending upon pH, rearrangement and disproportionation (acid-catalysed) of hydrazo intermediates have been highlighted as possible mechanistic pathway.

SEVERAL reductive pathways¹, e.g. H^+, e, e, H^+ , e, e, H^+, H^+ ; disproportionation proceeded by acid and/or base catalysed mechanism; anion and radical (dimerisation) with the uptake of 3 electrons at $pH > 7$, besides 4 electron transfer reaction commencing with the cleavage of $HN-NH$ bond have been proposed to occur. A broad based generalisation is yet to be established. The scope of another plausible explanation through rearrangement of intermediate hydrazo derivative at the electrode surface is described. A rearrangement of doubly charged protonated hydrazo derivative (at fairly low pH) to benzidine derivative has been worked out successfully on some symmetrically disubstituted azobenzenes in well buffered solution by employing various electrochemical techniques. The study has been extended to higher pH values as well in order to examine critically the mechanistic pathway.

Experimental

All electrochemical measurements were made with the apparatus using three-electrode configuration. Polarograms were recorded on a OH-105 Radelkis universal polarograph equipped with DME having the following capillary characteristics: $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 1.072 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$ in 1.0 M NaClO_4 at $h = 42 \text{ cm}$ when short-circuited. Controlled potential electrolysis² and coulometric experiments were performed with a Wenking LB 81M potentiostat employing a Hg-pool working electrode, $A \approx 20 \text{ cm}^2$. Cyclic voltammetry was performed with a CSIO instrument coupled with Omnigraphic 2000 X-Y/t recorder. In cyclic voltammetric experiments, HMDE ($A = 0.042 \text{ cm}^2$) was used as working electrode.

Spectrophotometric measurements were made with a Pye-Unicam SP 8-100 spectrophotometer.

A pH820 Trombay electronic pH meter equipped with a general purpose glass electrode was used for measuring pH. All potentials refer to Ag, AgCl,

Cl^- (saturated NaCl agar bridge) electrode. A temperature of $15 \pm 0.1^\circ$ (unless stated otherwise) was maintained.

Azo compounds, 2,2'-dichloroazobenzene and 2,2'-dimethylazobenzene (BASF) were purified by repeated crystallisation from 50% alcohol and dried over BaO in vacuum desiccator for several days. Purity determined by potentiometry was found in the range 99.4–99.5%. All other reagents used were of AnalaR grade. NaClO_4 was used as supporting electrolyte, adjusted to $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M}$. Buffer (Britton-Robinson)³ consisted of phosphoric acid, acetic acid, boric acid and sodium hydroxide. Low concentrations of azo compounds⁴ were used in electrochemical measurements as safeguard against pronounced aggregation phenomena.

Results and Discussion

D.C. polarograms of azo compounds were recorded over a pH range 1.9–9.3. No maxima was observed in the entire pH range. Only a single wave was noticed during investigation. Limiting currents as well as $E_{1/2}$ showed pH dependence. In pH range 1.9–3.9 wave height corresponded to two-electron transfer process, whereas at $pH > 4$ current showed a marked enhancement (≈ 2 times).

Concentration dependence of polarographic wave of azo compounds studied in 0.02–1 mM range at pH 3.2, 6.5 and 9.2 was found to bear a linear relationship. Temperature coefficient of 1.5 and 1.3% K^{-1} for chloro and methyl substituted azo compounds respectively was obtained in the temperature range 5–15°. In both the cases, linear relationships between current and $h^{1/2}$; current and $t^{1/6}$ at pH ranges stated above, suggest the reduction to be diffusion-controlled, whereas log plots resulted in a slope value of 33–37 mV (pH 1.9–3.9) indicates the process as irreversible. At $pH > 4$, slope dropped to 20–24 mV, a value higher than that expected for four-electron transfer process thereby predicting polarographic irrever-

sibility. $E_{1/2}$ -pH relationships (Table 1) have been worked to be of general nature* and warrants no special explanation.

TABLE 1— $E_{1/2}$ -pH RELATION		
pH	2,2'-Dichloroazobenzene	2,2'-Dimethylazobenzene
1.9-6.8	$E_{1/2} = 0.075 - 0.1$ (pH \pm 0.005)	$E_{1/2} = 0.10 - 0.12$ (pH \pm 0.006)
7.2-9.3	$E_{1/2} = 0.085 - 0.09$ (pH \pm 0.006)	$E_{1/2} = 0.13 - 0.11$ (pH \pm 0.006)

Controlled potential electrolysis: Controlled potential electrolysis of 2,2'-dichloroazobenzene in Britton-Robinson buffer of pH 2.8 (also extended to pH 3.2, 3.6 and 4) was carried out at potential -0.25 V vs Ag, AgCl, Cl at the beginning of plateau of wave ($E_{1/2} = -0.21$ V) and continued till the cell current decayed to less than 10% of its original value. Electrolysis yielded a product giving a characteristic λ_{max} (not so sharp) at 285 nm when dissolved in alcohol which corresponds fairly closely to the reported 3,3'-dichlorobenzidine absorption maxima⁵. Electrolysis product of 2,2'-dimethylazobenzene resulted in a peak (broad) having $\lambda_{max} = 289-292$ nm which compares with 3,3'-dimethylbenzidine⁶. Further isolation of the compound gave on elemental analysis 3,3'-dichlorobenzidine, m.p. $127-28^\circ$ (lit.⁷ 132°) (Found: C, 56.00; N, 11.05. Calcd. for: C, 56.91; N, 11.07%) and 3,3'-bimethylbenzidine, m.p. 126° (lit.⁷ 129°) (Found: C, 79.01; N, 13.11. Calcd. for: C, 79.24; N, 13.20%). Measurement of decrease in concentration of electroactive compound with time and integration of current consumed in electrolysis made it possible to calculate the number of electrons ($n = 1.8 \approx 2$) involved in reduction of both the compounds. These observations could be attributed to rearrangement of hydrazo derivatives to benzidine derivatives. Similarly at pH 6.5 and 9.2, the electrolytic product gave λ_{max} at 293 and 238 nm which is in agreement with literature value of *o*-chloroaniline⁸ and *o*-methylaniline⁹ respectively. The number of electrons involved during reduction was calculated to be 4, comparing well with the *n* value obtained from log plot which obviously favours a distinctly different reaction course.

Cyclic voltammetry: As evinced from Fig. 1 a single cathodic peak having $E_p = -0.23$ V vs Ag, AgCl, Cl⁻ with no complementary anodic peak on reverse scan was observed at pH 2.8. The study of the effect of enhanced sweep rate ν from 0.025 to 1.5 V s⁻¹ on peak potential and peak current showed shift in E_p toward more negative potential with an increase in i_p . The anodic peak remained absent throughout the scanning range, suggesting the process as irreversible. Influence of change of buffer pH on cyclic voltammogram was found to shift cathodic peak towards more negative potential with anodic peak remaining absent invariably. Peak current i_p however showed an increase at higher pH values. Higher scan rate resulted in another small cathodic peak which could be attributed to

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of 3,3'-dichloroazobenzene at pH: (1) 2.9 v 0.15, (2) 6.5 v 0.15, (3) 9.2 v 0.15 and (4) 6.5 v 1.5 V s⁻¹.

hydrazo intermediate formed during reaction. Further, an increase in i_p observed with the increase in reactant concentration and almost constant current function ($i_p/\nu^{1/2} C$) conclude in favour of diffusion-controlled process.

Electrode mechanism: At low pH range (Scheme 1), the reactant (1) undergoes initial $2e/2H^+$ transfer with the formation of the hydrazo derivative¹¹ (2). There seems to be a rapid rearrangement (2) to benzidine (4) in low pH range via an intermediate (3). Such reactions are known to occur in homogeneous solution with activation

Scheme 1

energy 20 kcal mol⁻¹ ¹². This viewpoint is also supported by value of *n* obtained polarographically and from cpe. The presence of -CH₃ and -Cl in the molecule having very small electron-releasing and electron-attracting tendency of the substituents in azo compounds favour 4,4'-coupling product rather than 2,4'- or 2, N'-product¹³.

At pH > 4 and < 9.3, the hydrazo derivative (2) so formed in first step undergoes acid-catalysed disproportionation reaction to *o*-substituted-aniline (6) and quinoid type intermediate (7) which stabilises to the aniline derivative (6) by uptake of further 2e and 2H⁺ as proposed (Scheme 1), consuming 4 electrons for conversion to aniline derivatives.

The possibility of remote homogeneous reaction could not be ruled out in which quinoid intermediate (7) reacts with hydrazo derivative to result in substituted-aniline(s) (6) and regenerating the parent compound (1) during the life of a drop.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A.R.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for a Associateship.

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